

FABRICATION - STRUCTURE - PROPERTIES CHAIN FOR BORON/ALUMINIUM STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

The present paper reports:

- a micromechanical failure model for a metal matrix composite;
- fabrication and mechanical properties (tensile and compressive strength) of boron/aluminium tubes;
- design of long metal-matrix-composite tubes to prevent a decrease in the compressive strength.
- design of fitting ends of the tubes.

FAILURE MODEL

A micromechanical failure model [1] connects mechanical properties of a composite and mechanical behaviour of a structural element with composite microstructure determined by physical and chemical interactions between the fibre and matrix during fabrication process and/or heat treatment. The ways of the interactions are numerous, and in a particular composite system, there can be observed peculiar patterns of the behaviour, in the addition to well-known features like a brittle interface formation. In a boron/aluminium composite with a matrix alloy containing an element that can bound chemically to a fibre element more easily than to a main matrix element (magnesium being a common example), a zone of the modified matrix around a fibre occurs. The material in such a zone, being dispersially hardened by borides, is characterized by larger strength than the original matrix, but it is much more brittle. This means that the heat treatment of boron/aluminium composites yields, at the beginning, an increase and then a sharp drop in the composite strength because of the growth and consequent linkage of the zones.

This is illustrated in Fig.1. The lines OA_1A_0 and $OB_1B_0D_0$ correspond to the ultimate stress for fibre breaks accumulation mechanism and that for the first fibre break, respectively. The lines A_0B_0 and A_1B_1 present the ultimate stress for composites containing characteristic microcracks of length l_0 and l_1 , respectively ($l_0 < l_1$). Suppose, at some stage of the fabrication process we have a composite with fibre volume fraction v_f' and the characteristic microcrack of length l_0 . Thus, the composite strength corresponds to point C_0 . Suppose now that the length of the characteristic microcrack changes from l_0 to l_1 , as a result of the coalescence of two zones around

the fibres. One can see that the composite strength goes from point C_0 to point C_1 . Because the coalescence takes place by a jump, there occurs a sharp drop in the strength at some point of the fabrication process or heat treatment. The strength/fibre-volume-fraction dependence going along the line $OA_1A_0B_0D_0$ before the drop, takes the path $OA_1B_1B_0D_0$ after the drop. In particular, this sets limits to the time/temperature profile during the fabrication process.

Figure 1. Schematic of the composite strength - fibre volume fraction dependence.

A further illustration of the process is presented in Fig 2 which shows a sequence of the events during the fabrication process by picturing the growing zones around the fibres and plotting corresponding changes in the strength/fibre-volume-fraction dependencies presented in the format of Fig.1. Because of an increase in the matrix strength due to formation of the hardened zones, point O moves up and the location of the line OA_0A_1 changes. This yields an increase in the value of a maximum composite strength and shifts the critical fibre volume fraction further to the left (consider the second stage of the events in Fig.2). After global linkage of the hardened zones has taken place, the critical fibre volume fraction becomes very low and real composite strength goes down to lower values.

To support these considerations, we present also Figs. 3 and 4 [1]. The first one shows dependencies of the composite strength on the time and temperature of a heat treatment, and the second one reveals sharp decrease in the strength of boron/aluminium when the size of the hardened zone reaches a half of the mean distance between the fibres. Perhaps data presented in Fig.4 are the most convincing.

To apply effectively the knowledge just outlined to the projecting of a particular fabrication technology, one has to get answers to the following questions: which equations do control the location of the characteristic lines drawn in Figs. 1 and 2, and how the growth of the hardened zones around the fibres can be evaluated?

The answers are given in Ref [1]. First, the mean strength of the composite corresponding to the fibre break accumulation mechanism (line OAA) is

$$\langle \sigma^* \rangle = \alpha \langle \sigma_f^*(l^*) \rangle v_f + \sigma_m^* v_m$$

where $\langle \sigma_f^*(l^*) \rangle$ is the mean fibre strength on length l^* , l^* is the average distance between fibre breaks, σ_m^* is the matrix strength, α is a constant. The location of the limiting curve AB is described by a Griffith - Orowan type equation, that is

$$\langle \sigma_n^* \rangle = \sqrt{\frac{CG}{\lambda nd}}$$

where C is a known function of the components of the tensor of elastic modulus tensor, and G is the effective surface energy of the composite.

Figure 2. Schematic presentation of the events and their consequences during a fabrication process of boron/aluminium composites. The time increases from top to bottom of the picture. The left column illustrates the formation of the hardened zones around fibres, their growth and coalescence. The corresponding changes in the failure behaviour of the composites are shown in the central column, which presents the evolution of the diagram shown in Fig. 1. Starting from the second stage, each graph shows a previous and a present situation. One can see how the matrix strength increase and the limiting curve (AB in Fig. 1) shift to the left effect a maximum value of the tensile strength that can be achieved at a particular stage of the fabrication.

Figure 3. Strength of boron/aluminium composites with Al - 6%Mg matrix versus heat treatment time and that versus heat treatment temperature (the heat treatment time is 30 min).

Figure 4. Strength of boron/aluminium composites with Al - 6%Mg matrix as a function of size of the hardened zone around a fibre in the matrix.

Experiments performed with ordinary specimens allow, first, to introduce the equivalent time, τ , as

$$\tau \propto \int_0^t \exp(-Q / RT(t)) dt$$

where Q is the activation energy of diffusion of boron in aluminium, and second, to establish dependencies of mechanical properties on τ . Provided the latter has been done, one can freely change the time/temperature profile of the fabrication process of a structural element, such as tube, just remaining within permissible interval of τ .

BORON/ALUMINIUM TUBES

Tubes with longitudinal reinforcement are an effective mass saving application of boron/aluminium composites in the Space and aviation technology. There are at least three major contribution into a relatively high price of such elements that prevent wider applications of such composite elements. These are fibre cost, hand work for prepreg lay-out, and solidification. The results of the studies of relationships between fabrication regime, composite microstructure and mechanical behaviour of the composites have yielded a new fabrication method of boron/aluminium structural elements that has been developed at Solid State Physics Institute, Chernogolovka, Russia.

FABRICATION

Composite tubes are now producing without using hot isostatic process that requires an expensive equipment. Tubes with the outer diameter of 20 to 75 mm and the length up to 1.5 m are being fabricated in an ordinary furnace by using a die shown in Fig. 5. The main point is an appropriate choice of the fabrication regime as well as a substance to transmit the pressure on the composite blank.

Figure 5. The assemblage for producing boron/aluminium tubes in an ordinary furnace.

The time/temperature profile is controlled by monitoring the temperature at a reference point of the outer surface of the die. Keeping the input energy of the furnace as well as the boundary conditions (that is especially important for the cooling stage) constant, we can assume that the equivalent time given by the above written equation be a function of the maximum temperature T_0 (see Fig. 6).

TESTING

Figure 7 illustrates an effect of changing the maximum temperature of the outer surface of the die on the strength of boron/aluminium tubes under tension and compression. Tubes were loaded through aluminium fitting ends.

One can see a difference in the temperature regimes of the fabrication process corresponding to maximum strength values under tension and compression.

Figure 6. Schematic of the temperature change on the die and composite blank.

Figure 7. Strength of boron/aluminium tubes with Al-6%Mg alloy as a matrix versus the maximum temperature on the outer surface of the die.

DESIGN

Here we briefly discuss just two features of the tube design.

Tubes under Compression

It should also be noted that the compression strength of composite tubes with longitudinal reinforcement is strongly dependent on the tube length.

So a special design of the tube is necessary to prevent premature failure of long tubes [2]. Considering failure mechanisms of composite tubes with longitudinal reinforcement under compressive loads [2,4] it is easy to suggest a bamboo-type structure of the tube that does completely prevent failure at low loads [3,5].

Figure 8. The ultimate compressive stress versus length/radius ratio for boron/aluminium tubes. The length/diameter values for the tubes are 1200/40, 1000/65, 1500/75 and 300/30 (mm). The tubes have aluminium screw fittings at the ends for applying the axial load. (Experimental data after [3,4])

Fitting Ends

A variety of the fitting end designs has been tested. Despite there are known some solutions of the related mechanical problem (see, for example, Refs [5,6]) a large amount of the experimental work is still necessary to optimize the design. That shown in Fig.9 is an example of the fitting end that provides an appropriate load transfer if some precautions are beheld.

Figure 9. An example of the fitting end design for the boron/aluminium tube.

CONCLUSIONS

The main conclusions can be formulated as follows:

1. The structure and mechanical properties of boron/aluminium composites with Al-Mg alloy matrix are strongly influenced by fibre effect on the matrix structure. In particular, the tensile strength increases with increasing the time and/or temperature of the fabrication process until the hardened zones touch each other.

2. There can be introduced an equivalent time as a measure of the zone progressing. The equivalent time can be estimated in experiments with small specimens and then be used to evaluate fabrication regime (this is a subject of work in progress).
3. The failure load under compression of a composite tube with longitudinal reinforcement can be enhanced by using a bamboo-type design of the tube.
4. Fitting ends for metal-matrix-composite tubes can be designed to provide the load transfer to the tube with a small increase in a tube mass.

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